

Theory and preliminary evidence of Universe formation and our life patterns in relation to that formation

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Abstract

[Early cultures](#) (1) identified celestial objects with gods and spirits, they related these objects and their movements to phenomena such as rain, drought, seasons, and tides. In this paper, I will identify the beliefs of humans around the years 250 A.D.-4000 B.C about astronomy and the relationship between their way of thinking that could suggest that human brains affected with magnetic fields that could have been one of the major factors in universe formation. I will also provide evidence that the key building blocks of life (5 Genetic letters of DNA) found in meteorites, which could have brought them to earth. In recent history, in 1960, [the Big Bang Theory](#) (2) was introduced and became as widely accepted model for the origin and evolution of the universe. It states the universe came into existence creating time and space, where it was extremely hot in the beginning, it expanded, and then cooled. It is estimated as per current observation the [age of the universe](#) (5) as 13.7 billion years. In this paper I will provide information on universe formation, theories, and simulation on the possibility that magnetic fields helped to form stars, planets, and where the magnetic fields may originally come from.

Introduction

First, I would thank you for your time to read this article. It constitutes of a theory and initial evidence on how the universe may have formed and our connection to that formation. My theory suggests the universe formed with magnetic fields, chemistry, space, and time. I believe these factors may resemble our life patterns in thinking and acting within our lifespan on earth. I have included in this article probable related evidence that I collected from articles and publication that shared discoveries and theories by other scientists, which could support my theory. I completed a Mechatronics course and have been reading books related to chemistry and earth science. I hope this article may add value to Astronomy and Astrobiology community.

Observations and Key findings

1. When Astronomy emerged as first nature sciences it started to play important roles to determine time, day, month, year, for people, governments, and agricultural societies. For example, Maya astronomical [codices](#) (4) include detailed tables for calculating the phases of the moon. The maya believed that the earth was center of all things. All civilizations had certain characteristics mainly was large [population centers](#) (10), in addition to shared communications, strategies, and other characteristics. Today, cities around the world are not different, with more organization and sophisticated communications and transportation means, people move locations and careers within communities. Newly born generations learn and follow the habits of previous generation, and adapt to contemporary ways of life that result from development. [Trees](#) (27) are the largest and oldest growing

thing on earth. They are round from the trunk because wood layers grow outward from the center, and has several characteristics similar to humans including living in [communities](#) (11). Scientist found evidence that [human brain can sense](#) (12) earth magnetic field through scanning the magnetic field around the brain. Recently, a state-of-the-art analytical technique allowed [scientists to detect](#) (20) all the pyrimidines and purines (Nucleobases) found in [DNA and RNA](#) (21) in meteorites that made it to the earth.

2. In 2012, the [Higgs Boson](#) (3) was discovered as the fourth particle that kept our universe from collapsing. The [energy density](#) (5) of the universe at first moments was higher than the energy associated with the vacuum expectation value of the Higgs field. As the universe started to cool down, the energy density dropped, and thus the symmetries broken, and certain particles gained mass. As the universe was expanding, filled with Hydrogen and small amounts of Helium, [galaxies formed](#) (7) in the areas with high concentration of H and He. The [clouds in the early universe](#) (9) were larger and much denser than modern-day nebula. An individual [star formation](#) (8) happens when irregularities in the density of the cloud gas or magnetic disturbances causes a net gravitational force to pull the gas molecules closer together. The collapsing cloud separate smaller clouds, which each may become a star. The core of each cloud starts to rotate faster to conserve angular momentum. The contraction causes pressure to increase which causes the cloud of gas to heat up, making the mass fall into the center. As the core heats up, it begins to look like a star. However, in the [early universe](#) (9), the dense and massive regions of clouds caused the clumps not to split as they contracted, so only a single star formed from each one. As a result, the first stars were so colossal, and millions of times as bright as the sun. A recent theory [published](#) (13) by two astrophysicists suggested that if sufficient magnetic field generated by the collision of [neutron stars](#) (28) an exotic type of neutron star could be created. Although the origins of the magnetic fields in universe remain unknown, recent research through [simulation](#) (15) of plasma flow when it becomes dense and nonlinear, the field amplitude can rise from zero to a level where the plasma gets magnetized. As a result, the traditional dynamo mechanism can take over and raise the fields. Rings caused by the magnetic field such as [Saturn rings](#) (16) may [not clump](#) (17) due to [Roche limit](#) (18). Such [accretion disk](#) (19) around Saturn are found around neutron stars and [Black holes](#) (25). With regards to how planets may have formed, some of the positively charged particles carried with the hot winds blown from the forming disk of a star crash into one another clump into [larger objects](#) (22). Dust clumps become pebbles, then pebbles turn to larger rocks. The presence of gas help particles of solid materials to stick together forming the building blocks of planets. Previous research found that vast majority of our [solar system elements](#) (23) originated from meteorites produced from a single neutron star collision or merger, and backdated the event to 80 million years before the birth of the solar system, in the Milky Way. A new research found that star HD 222925, in the our solar system neighborhood, in the Milky Way, [contains 65 elements](#) (24), and confirmed the environment where those elements were produced in a supernova or merger of neutron stars.

Results and conclusion

We can conclude that ancient single neutron stars collisions or mergers may have seeded the Milky Way and our solar system with heavy elements. Those collisions and merges caused meteorites to make their way to and carry the DNA and RNA that needed for life. We also conclude that magnetic fields may have played a role in forming the first stars, galaxies, and later planets. The cosmic impact of the

magnetic fields may have left an effect on the nucleobase brought on the meteorites that resulted by neutron stars collisions or mergers. As noted, human brains can detect magnetic fields, and the tendency for humans live in communities and to follow certain communications and life trends may be worth to research. A new experiment conducted in the [quantum physics facility](#) (26) launched recently on the ISS, used magnetic fields and Cold Atom Lab to study ultra-cold atoms in new geometry. This facility could help to launch future experiments to study the effects of magnetic fields on atoms and clarify findings on this paper.

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